

Efficiency of a wastewater treatment system in a tannery industry

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Abstract: *Wastewater treatment has acquired a great interest in recent years, especially in treating those effluents that come from industrial activities with a high content of pollutants. Therefore, the objective of the research was to evaluate the efficiency of the wastewater treatment system of the tannery company Alianza Virgen de la Asunción S.C.R.L. The stages of tannery wastewater treatment were made up of: 1) Precipitation chemical process, 2) Filtration process by activated carbon, 3) Disinfection process by sodium hypochlorite and 4) storage in neutralization tanks. A daily sampling of the water process was carried out from January to October 2020. The samples were transferred to the TYPESA Peru laboratory where they were subjected to the test of sedimentary Solids (SS), total suspended solids (SST), Sulfides, Hexavalent chromium, Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD₅), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Fats and Oils. The pH and temperature values were taken in situ with pH meter and digital thermometer, with the premise of faithful accomplishment of the Supreme Decree N° 003-2010-MINAM and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 6). The results show that the recirculation water had a useful life of 10 months before final disposal, benefiting the surrounding communities and minimizing the consumption of raw water for the tannery process.*

Keywords: Tannery Industry; Wastewater; pH; neutralization; BOD₅; COD

1. Introduction

Water is considered a non-renewable natural resource, which is why in recent decades proposals have emerged that are based on the need to propose solutions that help mitigate the high rates of water pollution from industrial activities (Masoud, 2020).

One of the proposals that have emerged is the implementation and redesign of production processes using green chemistry (Zimmerman et al., 2020). In this sense, Sierra et al. (2014) describe that "Green chemistry is focused on the design of processes, preparation and use of chemical products with a lower pollution potential and environmental risk than traditional ones, based on different technologies" (p. 2).

The above is what allows us to understand the development of research that focuses on the study of wastewater, which is defined by Díaz et al. (2012) as:

...action and effect whereby man introduces pollutants, forms of energy or induces conditions in water directly or indirectly; involves detrimental alterations to its quality in relation to subsequent uses or to its ecological function (p. 81).

Therefore, the efforts of scientists are focused on the search for increasingly effective wastewater treatment and reuse in order to propose alternatives to reduce pollution in water bodies and to be used in basic activities such as agriculture (Iqbal et al., 2021).

The main wastewater treatment techniques are based on physicochemical and biological procedures (Muñoz et al., 2020), including: chemical precipitation of nutrients (Taipicña, 2019), filtration processes (Gikas, 2017), distillation (Leaper et al., 2019; Kalla, 2021; Ramlow et al., 2017), flotation (Chávez-Vera, 2017), reverse osmosis (Trishitman et al., 2020). Although recently emerging methodologies such as the up flow anaerobic reactor (Malik et al., 2016) have been implemented.

Now, in the context of Latin America, a problem that most companies dedicated to leather tanning face is the treatment of their liquid waste, as they use a large number of environmentally toxic chemicals in their processes, which produce significant amounts of hydrogen sulphide, ammonia, chromium and organic matter from the hides themselves, which mix with water during the process, requiring an abundant amount of liquid (Giaccherini, 2016).

In the Peruvian case, the tanning industry has generated economic income and social development in cities such as Trujillo, Lima and Arequipa (Heredia, 2017). Tanning is a chemical process in which animal skins are transformed into tanned hides, which are then used in the manufacture of various garments and accessories, forming raw materials for industries such as those dedicated to the manufacture of umbrellas, bowls, handicrafts and textiles. This requires the use of different substances for the process, the most commonly used of which include chromium and other plant-derived substances such as tannins (van Rensburg et al., 2020). At the national level, it has been possible to determine the problems with regard to the existing deficiencies in the treatment and final disposal of wastewater. Paucar and Iturregui (2020) explain: "The findings of the EDA demonstrate the poor water quality of the Peruvian coast, its rivers and the adjacent sea, due to the continuous increase of effluents from urban agglomerations" (p. 10). In the district of La Esperanza, belonging to the province of Trujillo in the department of La Libertad, Peru, there is a tannery company called Alianza Virgen de la Asunción SCRL, which has innovated a process of wastewater treatment through the method of constant neutralisation, making use of the filtration technique, using activated carbon and sodium hypochlorite. The water derived from this treatment is recirculated back into the tanning process and continues for an extended period of time. When the liquid has finished its useful life in the process, it is sent to an oxidation lagoon and finally delivered to the community organisation for crop irrigation.

The practice of the company in question seems to be an alternative from the perspective of green chemistry that allows the treatment and reuse of wastewater from the tanning industry. In the light of this presentation, the question arose as to whether the company's wastewater treatment process is efficient. In order to answer this question, the research objective was to evaluate the efficiency of the wastewater treatment system of the tanning company Alianza Virgen de la Asunción SCRL.

2. Materials And Methods

The research was presented through a quantitative perspective, being of an evaluative type with a non-experimental design. Fundamental elements are presented below: the area of study and the phases of the research with each of the methods and materials used for its development.

Study Area

The study area corresponds to the tannery company Alianza Virgen de la Asunción SCRL, which is located in Manzana C Lot 5 of the Industrial Park La Esperanza, specifically located in the district of La Esperanza, belonging to the province of Trujillo in the department of La Libertad, Peru (Figure 1). In terms of climatic characteristics, the climate type is BWh (warm arid) according to the Köppen classification, with minimum temperatures of 15.7 °C and maximum temperatures of 22.9 °C and annual rainfall not exceeding 5.2 mm.

Figure 1. Water reuses base reuse system in laundries (Adapted from Google Earth)

The company in question has developed a wastewater treatment process that allows for the recirculation of water through a joint

process resulting in constant neutralisation. The water is first diverted to a chemical precipitation process, as carried out by Nur-E-Alam et al. (2020), and then goes through a filtration phase with the use of activated carbon, and finally sodium hypochlorite is added. This implies savings in tanning, as 760 m3 of raw water can be used for a prolonged period of production. At the end of each process, the water is deposited in a neutralisation tank, once treated, it enters the tanning process again.

The water ends its useful life when it reaches a pH equal to or below 6, as the company has established that once these levels are reached, the water must be withdrawn to an oxidation lagoon, which is then delivered to the community organisation for crop irrigation.

Figure 2 illustrates the water recirculation process within the tanning process in the company as described above.

Figure 2. Water recirculation process within the company (Based on field observations).

Phases of the investigation

The research was carried out in three phases, one in the field, which consisted of the collection of samples *in situ*, and another in the laboratory where they were processed. Each of these phases is described in detail below.

Field Phase

In situ sampling was carried out daily from January to October 2020, the sample collection was accompanied by a prior measurement of pH and temperature with a pH meter and digital thermometer. Samples were collected in previously sterilised glass containers with a capacity of 1 litre. Samples were taken at a depth of 20 cm, with the mouth of the bottle directed against the natural flow and horizontally (APHA, AWWA and WEF 1998), after which they were labelled. For the transfer of the samples.

For the transfer of the samples to the laboratory, the containers were placed in a hermetically sealed system with water ice at a temperature of 0 °C to ensure the preservation of the micro-organisms.

Laboratory Phase

For the development of this phase of the research, the services of a private laboratory accredited by the National Institute of Quality (INACAL), whose name is TYPESA Peru, were contracted. Table 1 shows the parameters determined with their respective method and treatment technique.

**Table 1
Analyses sent to the laboratory by method and technique used**

Parameter	Unit	Method	Technique
Settleable solids (SS)	mg _{SS} /L	SMEWW-APHA- AWWA-WEF PART 2540 F. 23 ED 2017c	Solids. Settleable Solids

Total suspended solids (SST)	mg _{SST} /L	SMEWW-APHA-AWWA-WEF. PART 2540 D. 23 ED. 2017a	Solids. Total Suspended Solids. Dried at 103 - 105 °C
Sulphides	mg _{S²⁻} /L	SMEWW-APHA-AWWA-WEF. PART 4500-S2- D. 23 ED 2017d	Sulfide ion-Selective Electrode Method
Hexavalent chromium	mg _{Cr6} /L	SMEWW-APHA-AWWA-WEF PART 3500-CR B. 23 ED 2017b	Chromium. Colorimetric Method
Biochemical Demand (DBO ₅)	Oxygen mg _{O₂} /L	SMEWW· AWWA-WEF. PART 5210 B. 23 ED 2017e	Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) S-CWY. BOD Test
Chemical Demand (DQO)	Oxygen g _{O₂} /L	SMEWW· AWWA-WEF. PART 5220 D. 23 ED 2017g	Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) Classic Reflux Colorimetric Method
Fats and Oils	mg/L	SMEWW-APHA-AWWA-WEF PART 5520 B 23RD ED. 23 ED 2017f	Oil and Grease by Partition-Gravimetric Method

Note. Own elaboration

The results of these analyses were averaged and compared with DS 003-2010 which establishes the Maximum Permissible Limits for effluents from waste, domestic or municipal treatment plants.

3. Results

The average results per quarter are presented below to facilitate understanding and to determine the behaviour of the values in relation to the recirculation of process water.

Table 2 shows the measurements taken during the quarter from January to March, which corresponds to the entry of raw water into the process and the first constant neutralisation treatments, showing a pH of 7.4, which indicates neutral water, with temperatures of 26.54 °C, with physical-chemical values below the Maximum Permissible Limit standardised by the national regulation of DS 003-2010 (Ministry of the Environment [MINAM], 2010). The results allow us to establish that the procedure is effective with respect to the reduction in raw water consumption throughout the first quarter in relation to pH.

Table 2
Average recirculating water results from January to March

Parameter	Result	Units	Maximum Permissible Limits DS 003-2010
Temperature	26.54	°C	<35
pH	7.4	pH	6.5 – 8.5
Settleable solids (SS)	1.7	mg _{SS} /L	8.5
Total suspend solids (SST)	11	mg _{SST} /L	150
Sulphides	<0.0007	mg _{S²⁻} /L	1,0
Hexavalent chromium	<0.001	mg _{Cr6} /L	0.5
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (DBO ₅)	26.3	mg _{O₂} /L	100
Chemical Oxygen Demand (DQO)	97.1	g _{O₂} /L	200
Fats and Oils	<0.6	mg/L	20

Note. Based on laboratory results

Table 3 shows the average results for the period from April to June. It can be seen that after the first quarter the recirculation water

tends to alkalise, reaching pH 8.1, but remaining within the Maximum Permissible Limit standards. The temperature of 29.01 °C corresponds to the expected temperature derived from the pH obtained. The values of Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD5) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) had a downward trend due to the alkalinity of the water. However, they are well below the standardised values of DS 003-2010.

Table 3
Resultados promedio del agua de recirculación entre abril y junio

Parameter	Result	Units	Maximum Permissible Limits DS 003-2010
Temperature	29.01	°C	<35
pH	8.1	pH	6.5 – 8.5
Settleable solids (SS)	1.3	mg _{SS} /L	8.5
Total suspend solids (SST)	7	mg _{SST} /L	150
Sulphides	<0.0001	mg _{S²⁻} /L	1,0
Hexavalent chromium	<0.001	mg _{Cr6} /L	0.5
Biochemical oxygen demand (DBO ₅)	23.6	mg _{O₂} /L	100
Chemical oxygen demand (DQO)	92.2	g _{O₂} /L	200
Fats and oils	<0.5	mg/L	20

Note. Base don laboratory results

The measurements made between July and September are presented in table 4. It is evident that the process water has dropped again to neutral pH levels with a pH of 6.8, which seems to indicate a downward trend. The temperature correlates with the pH scale, having a result of 26.37 °C. Once again, the results related to Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD5) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) had an upward behaviour, which is correlated with the pH value obtained. It is important to understand that, despite these variations, the levels remain within the stipulations of DS 003-2010.

Table 4
Average recirculation water results from July to September

Parameter	Result	Units	Maximum Permissible Limits DS 003-2010
Temperature	26.37	°C	<35
pH	6.8	pH	6.5 – 8.5
Settleable solids (SS)	2	mg _{SS} /L	8.5
Total suspended solids (SST)	13	mg _{SST} /L	150
Sulphides	<0.0007	mg _{S²⁻} /L	1,0
Hexavalent chromium	<0.002	mg _{Cr6} /L	0.5
Biochemical oxygen demand (DBO ₅)	26.1	mg _{O₂} /L	100
Chemical oxygen demand (DQO)	96.9	g _{O₂} /L	200
Fats and Oils	<0.5	mg/L	20

Note. Based on laboratory results

The last measurement was carried out in October (table 5), because the results showed a pH 6, i.e., with a tendency to acidification. The value is outside the Maximum Permissible Limits, and according to the company's own regulations, all process water with a pH equal to or lower than 6 must be sent to the oxidation lagoon. The temperature remains within the ranges corresponding to the pH, being 27.12 °C, however, the values related to the Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD5) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) did have a considerable variation, although they remain within the range ordered by the D.S. 003-2010. This makes it possible to establish that, at the end of the month, the water will be deposited in the oxidation lagoon and raw water will be reintroduced to start the procedure.

Table 5
Average recirculation water results month of October

Parameter	Result	Units	Maximum Permissible Limits DS 003-2010
Temperature	27.12	°C	<35
pH	6	pH	6.5 – 8.5
Settleable solids (SS)	2	mg _{SS} /L	8.5
Total suspended solids (SST)	13	mg _{SST} /L	150
Sulphides	<0.0007	mg _{S²⁻} /L	1,0
Hexavalent chromium	<0.002	mg _{Cr6} /L	0.5
Biochemical oxygen demand (DBO ₅)	35.15	mg _{O₂} /L	100
Chemical oxygen demand (DQO)	125.16	g _{O₂} /L	200
Fats and Oils	<0.5	mg/L	20

Note. Base don laboratory results

Figure 3 shows the graph that allows a better understanding of the variability of the results obtained in the recirculation period (January - September). The pH values are within the permitted ranges; however, it can be observed that from October onwards there is a tendency towards acidification. However, the rest of the values such as temperature, Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD5) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) remain within the standard, the pH is the one that helps to determine the efficiency of the wastewater treatment process in this research.

Based on the results, it can be established that the wastewater treatment process in the tannery Alianza Virgen de la Asunción SCRL is effective for the recirculation of water in a period of 9 months. Because an approximate raw water saving of 6849 m3 is being made for each ton produced during this period of time, which also has a direct impact on the reduction in the generation of wastewater.

Figure 3. Average results of pH, Temperature and Biochemical Oxygen Demand and Chemical Oxygen Demand in the measurement periods. Source: Elaborated from the results obtained in the laboratory.

In addition, the efficiency of the wastewater treatment with the constant neutralisation technique can be observed, in the saving of water resources, demonstrating that the process water reaches a useful life of 10 months, but, in addition, its final destination for the irrigation of community crops is an added value in the process; therefore, the company demonstrates what the World Bank establishes (2020):

...wastewater treatment has a dual value. In addition to environmental and health benefits, it can offer economic benefits through reuse in different sectors. Its by-products, such as nutrients and biogas, can be applied to agriculture and used for energy

generation (p. online).

The company in the process of water recirculation by the technique of constant neutralisation contributes locally to the fulfilment of SDG 6 clean water and sanitation. The company consumes less raw water for the tanning process, which together with the action of donating wastewater that is no longer suitable for industrial activity to neighbouring communities, is contributing to a win-win relationship within the framework of sustainable development. These ideas are supported by (Vergine et al., 2017; Michetti et al., 2019; Ofori et al., 2021; Arena et al., 2020) on the positive impact that the reuse of treated wastewater in agricultural activities can have.

In the ten months of measurements, an almost neutral pH behaviour was observed through the constant neutralisation process, which allowed the machinery to operate in optimal conditions. This is why the company has developed its internal policy on process water with standards above pH 6, because with higher acidification levels, corrosion would occur to the infrastructure (Pojtanabuntoeng, 2017).

As for the Biochemical Oxygen Demand, the results, even when they increased, remained below the Maximum Permissible Limits, which allows establishing the efficiency of the method in relation to the chemical process. Similar results are reported by research such as those carried out by (Zhao and Chen, 2019), who, despite working with highly polluting urban effluents, established the efficacy of activated carbon within the wastewater filtration process.

This indicator is fundamental because it provides insight into the efficiency of the process, as according to Goffin et al. (2014): "Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD5) is an empirical assessment of the dissolved oxygen consumed by microorganisms during the oxidation of reduced substances in water" (p. 8766).

The implementation of multiple methods for wastewater treatment is effective in obtaining favourable results in the recirculation of process water. Chemical precipitation and activated carbon filtration, which in conjunction with the addition of sodium hypochlorite, is emerging as one of the procedures that can help contribute to the development of a sustainable society. The proposed statement is supported by Jaramillo and Restrepo (2017):

One of the most widely recognised benefits of wastewater use in agriculture is the associated decrease in pressure on freshwater sources; furthermore, wastewater reuse increases agricultural production in regions experiencing water scarcity, which contributes to food security (p. 4).

Therefore, according to the research results, the process of wastewater treatment for recirculation within the tannery industry production is possible and can meet national regulations through technical treatment for recirculation. This idea is further reinforced by what Zhao and Chen (2019) explain: "...discharged tannery wastewater can meet the most stringent requirements and can be recycled by technical treatment as a whole." (p. 26110) and despite the belief that technologies for wastewater treatment can be very costly for the company, in the short term the performance and savings of the liquid are beneficial for the environment and the organisation.

4. Conclusions

The wastewater treatment process in the tanning company Alianza Virgen de la Asunción SCRL was standardised through the recirculation of process water and minimisation of raw water consumption, demonstrating the effectiveness of the neutralisation and final disposal of the input. The company, with the established process is benefiting the surrounding communities in meeting the objectives of sustainable development in relation to clean water and sanitation, therefore, consumes less raw water for the tanning process. The effectiveness of this treatment system is evident in the saving of water resources during the process, which was demonstrated in a useful life of 10 months through constant neutralisation for industrial processes, but, in addition, its final destination for the irrigation of community crops is an added value in the process; therefore, the company demonstrates the treatment of wastewater with a double value. In addition to the environmental and health benefits, it has a positive impact on the company's productivity and finances, the most representative aspect being the safety of its final disposal in the common drainage system. The final recommendation for other companies in the tanning sector is to maintain control and surveillance of the physicochemical parameters hydrogen potential (pH), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD5) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) based on the provisions of the sector's regulatory standards, specifically D.S. 003-2010.

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